

Twining Digital Subcarrier Multiplexed Optical Signals with OCATA for Lightpath Provisioning

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Digital Twins are needed in elastic optical networks to enable further advance and pave the way towards autonomous networks. Dynamical models self-adjusting with their physical counterpart have to maintain low computational complexity and guarantee good accuracy, regardless of the network topology and the technology supporting the optical lightpath. In this work, we propose data-driven models based on cascaded learning for single carrier signal as well as digital subcarrier multiplexing signals. Firstly, we explore the potentials of such a digital twin by proposing an algorithm for lightpath provisioning. In addition, the performance of the proposed models is compared with the one of analytical models. Secondly, we experimentally evaluate its accuracy to predict the impact of optical filtering penalties. The simulations show an overall good accuracy for different signal formats and demonstrate their viability for lightpath provisioning. Similarly, the experimental results demonstrate the feasibility of implementing such models to estimate the quality of transmission for digital subcarrier multiplexed signals.

Index Terms—Digital twin, digital subcarrier-multiplexing systems, quality of transmission estimation, lightpath provisioning

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital twins (DT) are arising as key enabling technologies for realizing smart manufacturing and Industry 4.0 [2] and, naturally, they attracted much interest in Elastic Optical Networks (EON) [3] to further increase the power and spectral efficiency, the robustness against failures, and to pave the way towards their full autonomy. A DT can be defined as a virtual, digital equivalent to a physical product [4]. Three key factors behind DTs are the low complexity models, telemetry data, and transfer learning (TL). In fact, they are built with low-complexity dynamical models designed to periodically self-adjust based on real-time telemetry data collected from their physical counterpart. Literature reviews and discussions regarding this emerging concept in the field of optical communications have been proposed recently in [5-7]. To summarize, DT enables optimized solutions during the design and operation of optical connections (*lightpath*) and has various applications, e.g., physical layer modeling (PLM) for quality of transmission estimation (QoT-E) [8,9], failure management [10], transmit power profile optimization [11,12], autonomous network control [13,14], among others. Examples of DT for EON include the open-source project GNPY [8], the time domain

OCATA [9] and the automation frameworks AI-light [11] and Auto-DTWave [15]. OCATA is a data-driven model based on Deep Neural Networks (DNN) that predicts how the linear interference (LI) and NLI noise from network components (i.e., reconfigurable optical add/drop multiplexers (ROADMs) and optical links) impact the in-phase and quadrature (IQ) components of optical constellations. Differently, GNPY is based on the Gaussian noise (GN) model [16] and estimates the generalized signal-to-noise ratio (GSNR) defined as the ratio between the channel power and the accumulated nonlinear interference (NLI) and amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise in a bandwidth equal to the symbol rate (SR). In [11], the authors exploited the GN model for SNR-based power optimization whereas in [15] to train DNNs employed for configuring autonomously the amplifiers with continuous wavelength loading.

EONs were conceived in the last decade supported by the availability of ROADMs based on wavelength selective switches (WSSs), and bandwidth variable transponders (BVTs) capable to transmit single-carrier (SC) signals [17]. BVTs introduced, for the first time, the possibility, among others, to adapt the modulation format (MF), the SR, and the forward error correction (FEC) configurations to the channel. On one hand, these features led to flexible spectral grid, and thus to a better usage of the available spectrum. On the other hand, these optical networks might present significant optical filtering penalties as a result of the narrowing of the transmission passband bandwidth, as a consequence of cascading numerous ROADMs in a single optical connection [18,19]. Filtering penalties need to be quantified in order to accurately design optical connections. However, empirical quantifications vary depending on the noise loading and thus result unpractical. To fill this gap, analytical models based on minimum mean-squared error (MMSE) equalization theory have been derived [20,21]. Alternatively, the authors in [22] tried to counteract the filtering penalties by jointly optimizing pre/post-digital equalizers and programmable WSSs. As technology advances, new generations of BVTs, which transmit digital subcarrier multiplexed (DSCM) signals instead of SC signals [23], have become available. Compared with its SC counterpart, DSCM transmission has better nonlinear tolerance [24] and potentially

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Fig. 1 Overview of the envisioned scenario.

allows each subcarrier to be independently operated [25]. If deployed on ROADM-based EON, DSCM signals are impacted by filter penalties similarly as SC signals [26]. In view of this, a joint pre/post-digital equalization scheme for filtering impairments was proposed for DSCM [27].

In this context, optical network DTs need to be upgraded to be able to predict the physical layer impairments that affect both SC and DSCM signals. Such capability would complement DTs in all their applications. For instance, during the lightpath provisioning phase, DTs can be used to predict the expected QoT of an optical signal before the lightpath is set up, and thus the optimal format of the signal to be transmitted, in terms of spectral efficiency and/or resiliency, can be found.

In our previous work [1], we exploited OCATA for QoT estimation (specifically for the pre-FEC bit error rate (BER)). Then, we extended the capabilities of the DT to model DSCM signals, and we proposed a new algorithm for lightpath provisioning. Equipped with such new models, we investigated the performance of SC and DSCM signals on realistic backbone EONs. In this work we extend our previous work presented in [1] by: 1) considering various MF besides 16QAM (e.g., QPSK and 64QAM); 2) verifying the suitability of OCATA for lightpath provisioning to decide which signal format (i.e., DSCM or SC) and which MF for a given route (ROADMs and optical links) - computed over the optical network topology - will be used; 3) exploring new approaches in the training of the OCATA DNN such as hyper parameter optimization and TL; 4) comparing the proposed models with other existing techniques; 5) experimentally analyzing the tolerance of DSCM signals to passband optical filtering penalties; and 6) validating the OCATA models for lightpath provisioning with experimental data.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the reference network scenario and the OCATA DT. Subsequently, Section 3 details the DT models for PLM and QoT estimation as well as the algorithms for lightpath provisioning. Section 4 contains the illustrative results that were obtained from optical constellation samples collected through both simulations and experiments. Finally, the main conclusions are given in Section 5.

Fig. 2 Optical spectra of SC (a, c) and DSCM signals (b, d) at the transmitter (top) and after cascaded WSSs (bottom).

II. EXTENDING OCATA FOR DSCM SIGNALS

Fig. 1 shows the reference network scenario. As physical layer, we consider an end-to-end lightpath between BVT-A and BVT-B that traverses N ROADMs and $N-1$ optical links using standard single mode fibers (SSMFs) and erbium-doped fiber amplifiers (EDFAs) as in-line amplifiers. We assume route-and-select (R&S) ROADMs with two WSSs and EDFAs as boosters and pre-amplifiers. On top, we assume a software-defined networking (SDN) control layer that monitors, configures, and orchestrates the optical devices. Moreover, we envision an additional layer where the DT operates, acting as a bridge between the other layers. OCATA features: (a) a telemetry database (DB) including optical constellation samples received from the SDN controller, which collects them from network agents located at the BVTs and at the ROADMs; (b) a model DB that contains: *i*) feature-extraction (FEx) models that characterize the optical constellation samples; *ii*) PLM models that estimate the noise introduced by the optical network components along the transmission line; and *iii*) models for QoT-E including regression and classification ones used to predict the Q-factor from the optical constellations; (c) a sandbox domain that is used for composing models with the ultimate goal of modeling specific lightpaths; (d) a set of algorithms for specific applications such as failure management [10], multi-domain knowledge sharing, and lightpath provisioning. The OCATA PLM models are based on cascaded

Fig. 3 OCATA strategy for the hyper parameter optimization of the cascaded DNNs.

Fig. 4 Transfer Learning Approach.

DNN, where each DNN describes a single ROADM or a single optical link (Fig. 1 (c)). DSCM signals, when compared to SC, are more robust against the NLI noise as in general they are working in the NLI “sweet spot” in terms of SR [28], i.e., from 4 GBd to 16 GBd per DSC. Even though the impact of the NLI noise is low, which leads to a mid-to-low performance penalty, other impairments (e.g., filtering distortions arising from the narrowing of the filter transmission bandwidth) play a critical role in EONs. For illustrative purposes, Fig. 2 shows the spectrum after BVT-A and the spectra after traversing several ROADMs for a SC signal (a,c) and a 16-subcarrier DSCM signal (b,d). As expected, the outer digital subcarriers (DSC) exhibit larger filtering penalties than the inner ones, which become more evident as the number of cascading filters increases. If the equivalent bandwidth of the filtering cascade is reduced by a value larger than the bandwidth of an individual DSC, then the edge subcarrier will be completely filtered out. On the other hand, the inner DSCs are mostly unaffected and can be used for reliable data transmission even after several WSSs. Therefore, differently to the SC transmission, where the whole signal degrades by filtering penalties, in DSCM transmission, such degradation is affecting only the external DSCs.

In view of the above discussion, it is important to provide models for the transmission of the different DSCs, particularly for propagation through ROADMs. For this reason, specific DNN models were considered depending on the signal under test: *i*) for the two *outer* DSCs (i.e., DSCs 15 and 16); *ii*) the two *intermediate* DSCs 13 and 14; *iii*) for the *inner* DSCs (i.e., DSCs from 1 to 12); and *iv*) for the SC signal.

This article further extends the OCATA DT [9] with models for DSCM signals and with an algorithm for lightpath provisioning. The goals of this work are the following: 1) to demonstrate the feasibility of OCATA DT to predict the QoT in EONs for lightpath provisioning applications; 2) to investigate the suitability of OCATA DT to model the filtering penalties affecting DSCM signals based on experimental samples.

Fig. 5 Models evaluated for QoT estimation.

III. MODELS AND ALGORITHMS

In this section, we detail the models employed for FEx, PLM, and QoT-E. Moreover, we propose an algorithm for lightpath provisioning.

A. Feature Extraction

An IQ optical constellation, denoted X and composed by a sequence of complex symbols $x \in X$, is a representation of an IQ modulated optical signal that encloses valuable insights regarding the condition of a given signal.

Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) can be exploited to extract information by characterizing m -quaternary constellations as a set of m bivariate Gaussian distributions. These latter can be summarized by a set of features $Y = \{Y_i\}$ for each constellation point (CP) i in m , where Y^i is composed of five semi-supervised constellation features representing the real and imaginary mean positions in the constellation (μ) and the real and imaginary variance values and symmetric covariance terms (σ), i.e., $Y^i = [\mu_1, \mu_Q, \sigma_1, \sigma_Q, \sigma_{1Q}]^i$. Relevant GMM hyperparameters are the number of clusters and the centroids that were set to m and initialized to the m -QAM ideal mappings (e.g., $[-3 -3i]$, ..., $[3+3i]$ for 16QAM), respectively.

To simplify the analysis, we consider only three DSCs under test: one inner, one intermediate, and one outer; and we extract a set of features for each of these DSCs. Note that additional features can be extracted such as the ones detailed in [10]. In this work, we employ the out-of-the-box probability feature Φ_{out}^i which computes the probability that a symbol transmitting the bit sequence encoded by CP i is detected at the receiver out of the detection area of such CP, denoted as A^i and is formally defined as follows:

$$\Phi_{out}^i = 1 - P(x \in A^i, x \sim N(Y^i)) \quad (1)$$

Moreover, we exploit the function $diff(X_r, X_e)$ that we proposed in our previous work [9], to compare received signals

Algorithm I. Lightpath Provisioning

INPUT: rq, ml, O **OUTPUT:** $format$

- 1: $Eval \leftarrow []$
- 2: **for** i **in** $[O.S]$ and j **in** $[O.MF]$:
- 3: $Y_e \leftarrow ml.generateY(rq.D, rq.N, rq.B)$
- 4: $\Phi_{out,e}[i, j] \leftarrow ml.processPhiOut(Y_e)$
- 5: $Q_{e,e} \leftarrow ml.QoTes(\Phi_{out,e})$
- 6: **if** $Q_e < O.th$ **then**
- 7: $Eval[i, j] \leftarrow ml.BitRate(O.MF, O.SR)$
- 8: **return** $getOptimalFormat(Eval, rq.R)$

Fig. 6 WSS transfer function used in the simulation (a), and filter shapes measured during the experiments from WS_1 (b).

(X_r) and the expected ones (X_e), by computing the Euclidean distance of the difference between the features extracted from X_r and the expected ones, given by:

$$diff_Y(X_r, X_e) = \|Y_r - Y_e\|_2 \quad (2)$$

B. Physical Layer Modeling

The set of features Y are propagated through the concatenated DNN, in particular the multi-layer perceptron (MLP), that models the impairments affecting the signals in an end-to-end lightpath, as shown in Fig. 1 (c).

Due to the different cascade filtering penalties involving the DSCs (see Fig. 2), differentiated ROADMs models are designed for the three considered DSCs and for the SC signal. In addition, differentiated link models are employed for the SC signal and for the DSCM signal due to the lower SR of the DSC.

The DNNs – that model the ROADMs and the links - were jointly optimized with Bayesian hyperparameter optimization (HPO) as detailed in Fig. 3. Bayesian HPO builds a probabilistic model of the function mapping from hyperparameter values to the objective [29]. In this work, we targeted as objective to minimize the average $diff(X_r, X_e)$ evaluated with 5-fold cross evaluation. By iteratively evaluating promising hyperparameters (e.g., learning rate, NN architecture, activation function, and optimization algorithm as detailed in [30]), the HPO finds a tuple of hyperparameters that yields an optimal model, which minimizes the $diff(X_r, X_e)$ function on a given independent data.

Moreover, OCATA can also benefit from TL. The usual TL approach detailed in Fig. 4 consists in training a *base* network and then copying its first n layers to the first n layers of a *target* network. The remaining layers of the *target* network are then randomly initialized and trained toward the *target* task. Note that TL can be a powerful tool to enable the training of a large target network without overfitting when the target dataset is significantly smaller than the base dataset [31]. Therefore,

when limited IQ optical constellation samples are available for a specific signal configuration (e.g., for a specific ASE level, or launch power) but plenty of IQ constellation samples are available for different signal configuration, TL should be employed.

C. QoT Estimation

Regarding QoT-E, we investigate three main strategies to estimate the Q-factor of the signal from the feature Φ_{out} , as detailed in Fig. 5: a) naive approach, in which the BER and the Q-factor are computed using the following expressions:

$$BER \sim \Phi_{out}^{avg} / \log_2(M) \quad (3)$$

$$Q\text{-factor [dB]} = 20 \cdot \log_{10}(\sqrt{2} \cdot \text{erfc}^{-1}(2 \cdot BER)) \quad (4)$$

where Φ_{out}^{avg} is the average out of box probability among the CPs, M is the M -quaternary modulation index and erfc^{-1} is the inverse complementary error function.

In Equation (3), the average out of box probability is interpreted as an estimation of the symbol error rate (SER) and the BER is derived assuming that 1 symbol error causes only 1 bit with error (which is reasonable when employing Gray coding). Finally, Equation (4) can be used to derive the Q-factor from the BER when the optical signals are perturbed by additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) [32]; b) DNN: we exploit a DNN with one hidden layer (also known as Shallow Neural Network) similarly to our previous work [10]. These networks receive as input the Φ_{out}^i features of four selected CPs, as well as the number of crossed ROADMs (N), and the overall propagation distance (D); and c) Binary Classifier. We exploit a binary classifier that receives as input Φ_{out}^i features of four selected CPs, N , and D to determine whether the FEC-threshold has been crossed. Specifically, we employed as binary classifier an ensemble combining random forest (RF) and gradient boosting algorithms (e.g., extreme gradient boosting (XGB) and AdaBoost (AB)) and use a majority vote to predict the class labels. Both these ML approaches were trained off-line with independent data and with hyper parameters optimized using Bayesian search.

D. Lightpath Provisioning Algorithm

Moreover, we propose an algorithm for lightpath provisioning which exploits the aforementioned models to identify the best format of the signal to be transmitted to provision a specific lightpath. Algorithm I receive as input: i) an optical connection request (rq) detailing the required data rate R , the selected route in terms of total length D and number of crossed nodes N , the SR , and the Q-factor threshold th ; ii) parameters and trained models (ml) stored in OCATA; and iii) operational parameters (O), including the allowed signal formats S (e.g., SC and DSCM) and MF . To address a provisioning request, the algorithm searches among the possible combinations of S and MF as given in the request.

For each possible configuration the algorithm generates the expected features Y_e and exploits them to compute the Φ_{out} feature (lines 2-4). The out-of-the-box probability feature together with other lightpath details are given as inputs to the aforementioned QoT-E models that are executed to estimate the

Fig. 7 Analysis of the Q-factor (a,b,c), the IQ constellation symbols' variance (d,e,f) and the standard deviation of the symbols' variance (g,h) as function of the cascaded WSSs.

pre-FEC BER (line 5). Finally, if the estimated Q-factor (Q_e) is below the Q-factor threshold th , then an *Eval* matrix is populated with the expected data rate achievable for each signal configuration and at the output of every node (lines 6-7). Finally, the *Eval* matrix is used to select the optimal signal format for the received connection request (line 8).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Numerical Study

1) Numerical Setup

A MATLAB-based simulator of a digital coherent system is employed to reproduce both SC and DSCM signal transmissions. In both cases, we consider a dual-polarization Nyquist-shaped channel with a roll-off factor of 0.06, operating at a SR of 64 GBd and using a single-wavelength architecture. The DSCM signal is composed of 16 DSCs, all operating at 4 GBd spaced with a guard-band of 100 MHz. The pulse propagation along the fiber is modeled by solving the Manakov equation using the split-step Fourier method with a propagation step-size of 1 km including effects such as fiber loss, arbitrary fiber birefringence, group velocity dispersion, polarization mode dispersion (PMD), and self-phase modulation. Each link consisted of 80 km SSMF spans characterized by a fiber loss coefficient of 0.21 dB/km, a dispersion parameter of 16.8 ps/nm/km, PMD value of 0.04 ps/km^{1/2}, and a nonlinear coefficient of 1.14 W⁻¹km⁻¹. The EDFAs' noise figure is 5 dB and its gain is set to compensate for the span loss and to restore the power to the launched one which is near-optimal (1 dBm for both SC and DSCM signals). Note that each DSC has a launch power of -12.2 dBm and that at the transmitter side we assume the same background noise both for SC and DSCM signals leading to a normalized optical signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) of 49 dB. At the receiver side, we considered digital signal processors (DSP) performing ideal chromatic dispersion compensation, ideal carrier phase recovery and equipped with a MIMO adaptive filter based on least-mean-squares (LMS) algorithm with optimized parameters.

In this analysis, we consider three M -quaternary MF with order of 4, 16 and 64, respectively. Moreover, we consider R&S ROADMs containing two filters: one $1 \times N$ route WSS steering

the incoming wavelength to the drop port or to another degree and one $N \times 1$ select WSS that can block unused wavelengths and add new ones. To emulate the filtering penalties, we consider the filter shapes of four different commercial 1×4 WSS shown in Fig. 6 (a) that were concatenated in the simulator with random patterns. These filter shapes (captured experimentally) have a -3 dB optical bandwidth of approximately 71 GHz and insertion losses of ~ 8 dB.

We repeat 20 times the simulations for each configuration. Note that for each repetition we store the IQ optical constellations composed of 218,450 symbols and optical spectra with 150 MHz resolution. Finally, the BER and the Q-factor were evaluated over 1,747,600 symbols for 16QAM and 64QAM (i.e., over 6,990,400 bits and 10,485,600 bits, respectively) and over 3,495,200 symbols for QPSK (6,990,400 bits). The raw data generated in this work is available in [33]. These data were exploited to build OCATA PLM models for inner, intermediate and outermost DSCs and SC signal with three MF following the methodology described in Fig. 3. For each configuration, the PLM models were trained and evaluated independently over more than 600 IQ constellation samples i.e., 20 repetitions \times 30 locations (at the input and output of 15 ROADMs).

Differently, the QoT-E models (e.g., DNN and ensemble) were trained and optimized over more than 10,000 independent IQ constellation samples (i.e., from the DSCs not considered in the analysis and from signals with a higher launch power).

2) Numerical Results

Fig. 7 (a,b,c) show the Q-factor as function of the number of cascaded WSS for different MF i.e., QPSK (a), 16QAM (b) and 64QAM (c). Note that the Q-factor values here reported, were obtained considering a minimum number of 100 errors. For illustrative purposes, we plot a pre-FEC Q-factor threshold at ~ 6.73 dB. According to the numerical simulations, the outermost subcarrier (i.e., DSC 15) was, as expected, the one most affected by the filtering effects for every considered modulation index and can traverse up to 7, 5, and 2 ROADMs (14, 10 and 4 filters) before reaching the pre-FEC threshold for QPSK, 16QAM and 64QAM, respectively. Note that the ROADMs are composed of two filters and two EDFAs, and were separated from each other by 80 km spans. In contrast, the

Fig. 8 Q-factor absolute error of OCATA for QoT monitoring based on DNN (a, b) and naive model (c, d).

Fig. 9 Q-factor absolute error of OCATA for lightpath provisioning based on DNN (a,b) and naive model (c,d).

internal and intermediate DSCs traverse all considered cascaded WSSs when modulated with 16QAM and QPSK, and up to 10 filters when modulated with 64 QAM. Aggregating the contributions of each DSC, we compute the average Q-factor of the whole DSCM signal for illustrative purposes. As for the SC signal, it supports traversing up to 12 and 4 cascaded ROADMs before reaching the pre-FEC threshold for 16QAM and 64QAM, respectively and all cascaded WSSs when modulated with QPSK. Note: we observe that for the highest MF (i.e., 64QAM), both DSCM and SC signals degrades similarly mainly due to propagation effects (e.g., ASE, NLI, etc.) and due to the ASE noise introduced by booster- and pre- EDFAs. Differently, for 16QAM signals filtering penalties limit the reach of SC signals and external DSCs but DSCM signals as a whole guarantee a capacity floor for the considered reaches. Finally, for QPSK signals filtering effects are visible but are not detrimental for the considered cases.

Fig. 7 (d,e,f) show the symbol variance σ characterizing the corner CP as a function of the number of ROADMs crossed for different MF i.e., QPSK (d), 16QAM (e) and 64QAM (f). We observe that σ exhibits a behavior mirroring the Q-factor which

Fig. 10 Actual and predicted Q-factor through OCATA for lightpath provisioning based on DNN (a, b, c) and naive model (d, e, f).

confirms what was found in our previous analysis [1] and extends it for QPSK and 64QAM signals. Moreover, Fig. 7 (g) and Fig. 7 (h) provide further analysis regarding the quality of FEx and its dependency with the dimension of the IQ constellation samples. In particular, the figures show that the standard deviation of the symbols' variance decreases as the IQ constellation dimension increases. For this reason, enough symbols must be employed to correctly characterize the IQ constellations with GMM. Moreover, the figures show that the standard deviation of the GMM-extracted features increases with the number of cascaded WSSs. Thus, suggesting that the GMM accuracy decreases as the physical impairment increases. Moving to the QoT-E models, we investigate their performance for two use cases: 1) QoT monitoring, where the out of box probabilities are directly computed from the monitored IQ optical constellations and 2) lightpath provisioning where the out of box probabilities are predicted by executing the OCATA PLMs. In this regard, Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show the nested inter quartile ranges of the absolute errors (AEs) obtained to predict the Q-factor for DSCs and SC signals based on the DNN model (a,b) and on the naive approach (c,d).

Fig. 8 shows that very accurate predictions were achieved in the QoT monitoring use case regardless of the model (i.e., DNN and naive). In fact, a maximum Q-factor AE below ~ 0.5 dB was obtained for both models and for almost all the configurations except for low Q-factors (e.g., below 5 dB). Differently, Fig. 9 shows the AEs obtained in the lightpath provisioning use case. As expected, we notice that the performance of the QoT-E models varies depending on the use case (i.e., QoT-monitoring and lightpath provisioning). In this case, we observe that the DNN achieve a maximum AE below ~ 0.8 dB for critical Q-factors (e.g., above 5 dB) outperforming the naive approach (it is more evident for 16QAM). On the contrary, for signals affected severely by physical impairments (e.g., Q-factors below 5 dB), GMM are less accurate and as a consequence OCATA models too. While these results give interesting insights regarding the error introduced by OCATA PLM models, they are not useful when one needs to evaluate the feasibility of a QoT-E model for applications such as lightpath

Fig. 11 Achievable gross data rate after 6 (a), 10 (b), 24 (c) and 26 or more cascaded WSSs (d) based on OCATA models.

Fig. 12 Comparison between OCATA models and analytical ones in terms of performance (a) and computational speed (b).

provisioning. In this case, the errors of the model should be related to the actual QoT values. In this regard, Fig 10 shows the actual Q-factor for DSCs and SC signals with different MF versus the median and the min max range of the predicted ones. Note that the OCATA predictions are less accurate for the external subcarrier (i.e., DSC15), in which the optical signal is affected by the most severe filtering penalties. Moreover, we observe that contrary to what has been anticipated, the DNN model (a,b,c) and the naive approach (d,e,f) show a similar performance. This is confirmed by Fig. 11, which shows that the lightpath provisioning algorithm achieves identical results employing naive or DNN model and diverges slightly employing the binary classifier. In particular, Fig. 11 compares the gross data rate according to simulations (labelled as ‘Actual’) and to the OCATA models after 6 (a), 10 (b), 24 (c) and 26 or more cascaded WSSs (d). Specifically, we evaluate the performance of the lightpath provisioning algorithm with the proposed QoT-E models (e.g., naive, DNN, and binary classifier).

We notice that the naive and DNN models predict an expected throughput that matches the simulations in all the cases but for the 64QAM DSCM signals after 10 cascaded WSSs (see Fig. 11 (c)). Moreover, these models support conservative QoT estimation, i.e., similar or lower Q-factor compared to the simulated one. On the other hand, the ensemble classifier incurs in errors several times (i.e., false negatives), which cause optimistic QoT estimation. In view of these remarks, the naive and DNN QoT-E models demonstrate to be more suitable for the lightpath provisioning task.

3) Comparing with Existing Methods

A comparative analysis with other techniques is included to understand the potential benefits of the proposed models. For this purpose, we compare the performances of the data-driven OCATA models with those of analytical models based on GNPpy and on the MMSE model. In particular, we use the GNPpy’s open-source implementation of the GN model [16] (“gn_analytic” function). The physical parameters given as input to GNPpy were the same set in the SSFM simulator (i.e., fiber parameters, gains and NFs of the EDFAs). As for the MMSE model we employ the equations available in [21], considering one spectral folding. The GSNR was computed through GNPpy while we considered two analytical transfer functions that are showed in Fig. 6 (a): the first based on the sixth-order super Gaussian function (SGF), with 70 GHz bandwidth and the second based on Pulikkaseril (PLK) model [34] with a 9.3 GHz optical transfer function and a 75 GHz channel bandwidth. Note that these transfer functions mimic the ones of the commercial WSSs employed in the simulator.

Fig. 12 (a) compares the Q-factors as function of the cascaded WSSs predicted by the considered models with the actual Q-factors obtained through simulations (considering a minimum of 100 errors). As for the accuracy, both OCATA and MMSE models provides accurate estimation while the GNPpy model is very inaccurate. This is due the fact that the GN model do not include formulas to estimate filtering penalties. Moreover, we observe that the MMSE model was more accurate when based to the PLK transfer function (that matches almost perfectly the actual one). Furthermore, Fig. 12 (b) compares the computation speed of the considered approaches as function of the cascaded WSSs. To obtain these results we used Python 3.9 on a workstation with a Core i7 1370P processor and 32 GB of RAM. Note that the codes used to implement the OCATA and MMSE models may be further optimized. Both OCATA and GNPpy models have an execution time that increases with the number of in-line filters. Conversely, the MMSE model has a steady execution time mostly due to the integration of the spectrally resolved GSNR. In view of these results, we observe that for the investigated scenario the proposed DNN-based OCATA models offer the most advantageous trade-off between accuracy and execution time.

Finally, Table 1 includes an overall comparison between the analytical GN model and the data-driven OCATA models. The GN model has a good maturity: it has been validated several times and has been exploited in multiple DTs frameworks. However, the GN model being a power model provides limited information on the signal and is not suitable for EONs with severe filtering penalties. In addition, the accuracy of analytical models (i.e., GN and MMSE) depends strictly on the correct quantification of physical parameters. Differently, OCATA models are data-driven and as such can be employed to model any communication link without knowledge of the physical laws or of the physical parameters. For these reasons, the mentioned approaches can be used complementarily. For example, when only limited information on the lightpath is

Table 1: COMPARISON OF GN-BASED ANALYTICAL MODEL AND OCATA DATA-DRIVEN MODEL.

	Analytical: GN-based model [16]	Data-driven: OCATA [9]
Strongpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Several validations of GN model. - Open-source implementation, i.e., GNPpy [8]. - Mature. Already tested in DT frameworks [11,13, 15]. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Give multiple insights on the optical signal. - Do not need knowledge of physical parameters. - Fast Inferencing Time.
Shortcomings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires physical parameters calibration (e.g., α, β_2, γ, NF). - Provide limited insights on the optical signal. - Do not include formulas to estimate filtering penalties. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Necessary to collect large datasets for offline training. - Low explainability.

Fig. 13 Experimental Setup (a) and OCATA models (b).

available OCATA should be used instead of GNPpy and MMSE models. Note that OCATA provide multiple analytics on the status of an optical signal (e.g., transmission distance [9]) and has a low inferencing time. The downsides of this approach are its low explainability and the need of extensive datasets for the training. In the next section, we will address questions still uncovered regarding the feasibility of such approach when considering real data and when only reduced data sets are available for training.

B. Experimental Study

1) Experimental Setup

The experimental data was obtained by using the setup shown in Fig. 13 (a). A single evaluation board (EVB) was employed both to transmit and receive all the 16 DSCs with a total launch power of 0 dBm and a total SR of 60.15 GBd. Note, that additional functionalities of the EVB to counteract filtering penalties (e.g., gain sharing, pre-emphasis) were deactivated. An optical circuit switch (OCS) routed the DSCM signal to a waveshaper (WS) emulating the filtering penalties arising from cascaded WSSs (labeled as ‘WS₁’ in Fig. 13). Then an EDFA (labeled as ‘EDFA₁’ in Fig. 13) was employed in automatic power control (APC) mode to compensate for the power losses introduced by WS₁ (~12 dB). The filtered DSCM signal was then coupled together with ASE noise, which was generated by an ASE broadband source, then filtered and finally amplified

with an EDFA (labeled as ‘EDFA₂’ in Fig. 13 (a)).

Moreover, two variable optical attenuators (VOAs) were employed: VOA₁ was exploited to control the received optical power at the receiver. VOA₂ was used to control the ASE noise level to be added to the signal and thus to sweep the OSNR at the receiver. Finally, the DSCM signal was broadcasted by optical splitters with splitting ratio 90:10 to the EVB, to a wave analyzer (WA) and to a power meter (PM). The data acquisition was automated by enabling communication between a machine and GPIB, Ethernet and USB devices.

The experimental setup was used to collect IQ optical constellation samples, power spectral densities (PSD) and QoT metrics for different configurations including different filter shapes and ASE noise values. Fig. 6(b) shows the actual filter shapes set in WS₁. These shapes were characterized experimentally by inserting broadband ASE in WS₁ and by averaging the PSD measured with the WA. These filter shapes were used to investigate the passband optical filtering penalties present in an optical network where DSCM optical signals have to cross several WSSs. In particular, we consider a number of cascaded WSSs ranging from 0 to 26 with a step of 2 (see Table 2). Note that in this work we consider a stressed scenario as we model WSSs as third order SGF whereas last generations of WSSs can be modeled as higher-order SGFs [34]. Conversely, a wide rectangular filter (e.g., 200 GHz bandwidth) was configured in WS1 to mimic the performance of an unfiltered DSCM signal.

Moreover, note that the overall DSCM signal ASE noise can be defined as:

$$ASE [dBm] = ASE_{ref} [dBm] + ASE_{load} [dB] \quad (5)$$

where ASE_{ref} is the ASE Noise measured in back-to-back while ASE_{load} is the additional ASE noise artificially added to the DSCM optical signal via ASE loading. Note that in this work considered the following ASE_{load} values: 0, 3, 12, 14, 16, 18 and 20 dB.

Finally, Fig. 13 (b) shows a representation of the OCATA model employed in the experiment. In this case, we trained two models: an ASE noise model that serves the purpose of modeling the LI noise introduced to the optical signal by the ASE broadband source, and a ROADM model for the filtering penalties introduced by two cascaded WSSs. Note that these DNNs were trained following the TL workflow described in the previous section. In particular for a specific ASE value, *target* models were built by copying the layers of a *base* model trained with all the remaining data and by adding new layers. The transferred feature layers were left ‘frozen’ (i.e., they do not change during training on the new task) in order to avoid

Fig. 14 ΔQ -factor and symbols variance as function of the filter bandwidth for external (a,d), intermediate (b,e) and central (c,f) DSCs.

Fig. 15 Accuracy of the TL-based OCATA models for PLM and QoT-E for external (a,d), intermediate (b,e) and central (c,f) DSCs.

overfitting as the target dataset is small. Relevant hyperparameters such as the number of the layers to be added and the number of epochs to be used to train the new layers were obtained through grid search HPO.

2) Experimental Results

Fig. 14 (a,b,c) show the relative Q-factor, ΔQ -factor as function of the WS -3 dB bandwidth for the three representative DSC (i.e., DSC 15, 13, 1). Note that ΔQ can be calculated using the following expression:

$$\Delta Q\text{-factor} = Q\text{-factor} - Q_{ref} \quad (6)$$

where Q-factor is the actual one measured on the experimental test bed and Q_{ref} is a reference value.

As expected, we observe that the external DSC (i.e., DSC 15) is the one most impacted by the narrowing of the transmission bandwidth compared to the intermediate (i.e., DSC 13), while the central one (i.e., DSC 1) does not exhibit degradations in terms of Q-factor. Fig. 14 (d,e,f) shows the feature I-symbols variance as function of the WS's bandwidth. Fig. 15 (a,b,c) depicts the actual ΔQ and the predicted one based on the OCATA models (i.e., ASE Noise model, ROADM model and QoT model). Moreover, Fig. 15 (d,e,f) illustrate the relative error (RE) in predicting the Q-factor as function of the number of cascaded WSSs. Interestingly, we observe that the OCATA model's RE tends to increase with the number of cascaded WSSs, and also for the configurations with more ASE noise

loading (i.e., $ASE_{load} \sim 18, 20$ dB). Note that these are the same conditions for which the GMM fitting produces features with the highest standard deviation.

Finally, Fig. 16 reports the required OSNR (ROSNR) that was observed experimentally cascading third-order super Gaussian filters. Moreover, Fig. 16 also shows the ROSNR estimated based on the OCATA models. As expected, the external and intermediate DSC present a ROSNR penalty that increases as the WS bandwidth decreases. On the other hand, the ROSNR penalty of the central DSC remains constant. Note that DSC 1 exhibits a slightly negative ROSNR penalty because the OSNR was measured over the whole DSCM signal bandwidth and not per DSC (the OSNR has some variations among DSCs). We observed that the OCATA predictions are more accurate for lower values of ROSNR penalty and in general for higher WS bandwidths.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We propose an extension of the OCATA time domain DT for optical connections based on DSCM signals in elastic optical networks (EON). The DT is composed by models for physical layer modeling (PLM) and quality of transmission estimation (QoT-E). The PLM models propagate features characterizing IQ constellations using cascaded deep neural networks (DNN), while the QoT-E models predict the Q-factor from these

Table 2 DETAILS ON THE FILTER -3 DB BANDWIDTHS SET IN WS_1 .

#WSS	-3 dB BW [GHz]	Bw/Rs
0	200.00	3.301
2	63.63	1.051
4	61.38	1.011
6	60.35	0.997
8	59.25	0.980
10	58.67	0.970
12	57.85	0.956
14	57.27	0.947
16	56.77	0.940
18	56.49	0.933
20	56.07	0.927
22	55.88	0.924
24	55.43	0.916
26	55.19	0.912

Fig. 16 Measured ROSNR Penalty for a target Q-factor of ~ 6.73 dB (continuous line) and estimated with OCATA (dashed line).

features. These models are exploited by a lightpath provisioning algorithm that has the goal to pinpoint the optimal signal configuration for a specific connection request.

In this work we generated data through simulations (now available in an open-access repository [33]) to train and test the models of the data-driven OCATA digital twin. Then, we evaluated the proposed models for a wide range of signal formats, namely SC and DSCM signals modulated using a variety of QAM formats, and we show that very high accuracy can be achieved despite of the error introduced in the PLM. Moreover, we analyzed the feasibility of employing these models for lightpath provisioning by investigating the impact of the Q-factor AE on the provisioning task. To do so, we assessed the performance of the OCATA algorithm to correctly predict the achievable throughput of different signal configuration, showing promising results. Moreover, the proposed models when compared with analytical ones showed the best trade-off between accuracy and computational speed.

Additionally, an experimental analysis was conducted to evaluate the proposed models when combined with experimental data. We investigated transfer learning models to overcome real world limitations such as reduced training dataset. We have observed that the proposed models provide a good accuracy which decreases with the accumulation of physical impairments (e.g., ASE noise and filtering penalties) in accordance with the simulations' results. Finally, these results show the feasibility of implementing OCATA in EON being a viable solution for designing optical connections.

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